

Edge Modes of MoS₂ via Indirect Double Resonant Raman Spectroscopy

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Abstract

We report a set of resonantly enhanced defect modes in the Raman spectrum of molybdenum disulfide (MoS_2) which are fully analogous to the D mode of graphene, allowing sensitive defect quantification and differentiation of zigzag and armchair edge structures. These modes become active at edges under indirect resonance conditions at 785 nm excitation due to strict backscatter constraints in real and reciprocal space, which exclusively select phonon wavevectors perpendicular to the edge direction. We assign features to single LA(K), TA(K), and TA(Q) phonons along the $\overline{\Gamma\text{K}}$ direction of the Brillouin zone and identify a separate pre-resonant enhancement of the whole spectrum along the $\overline{\Gamma\text{M}}$ direction, which is lost in thinner material as the band gap increases. In addition, we identify a clear incident polarization dependence of the K and M phonons, which suggests the presence of an inhomogeneous optical absorption analogous to that of graphene. We anticipate this indirect double resonance Raman technique will provide a powerful tool for materials characterisation, allowing quantification of active sites in catalytic MoS_2 and characterisation of the structure-dependent properties of MoS_2 nanomaterials. In addition, the intervalley scattering pathways provide a sensitive probe of the low energy landscape of the conduction band, and may reveal a wealth of electronic information and scattering dynamics important for spin-valley coupled systems. We anticipate similar modes can be found in other transition metal dichalcogenide systems, given the appropriate excitation energy.

1 Introduction

In the wake of two-dimensional (2D) materials research following the discovery of graphene, transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) such as MoS_2 have garnered particular interest in literature owing to their due to their semiconducting nature and remarkable range of applications, including photovoltaics,[1] optoelectronics,[2] catalysis,[3, 4] and emerging fields such as valleytronics for information storage via spin-valley polarization.[5, 6]

Consideration of defects in MoS_2 is necessary for many applications, as they can either be detrimental to device performances, such as through the quenching of photoluminescence and valley depolarization,[7] or greatly beneficial for controlling electronic properties[8–11] and improving catalysis. It is well known that the active sites for hydrogen evolution are in fact defects and edges, while the basal plane of MoS_2 remains relatively inert.[12, 13]

In addition, defects and grain boundaries have been shown to possess one-dimensional (1D) magnetic properties,[14, 15] while nanoribbons are predicted to possess differing magnetic properties depending on whether the edge structures assume armchair or zigzag configurations.[16, 17] Defect states can also induce enhanced spin-orbit splitting and lead to magnetic manipulation of the valley-pseudospins in defect-bound excitons.[8, 11]

Consequently, the ability to detect and quantify defects in MoS_2 is critical to the optimization of material performances. However, there are currently few convenient methods for characterizing defects and edges of MoS_2 materials, as they typically revolve around atomic-resolution imaging of localised defects,[18–22] or specialised optical experiments such as magnetic Raman mapping[23] and tip-enhanced Raman spectroscopy.[24]

Double Resonance Raman (DRR) describes second-order Raman processes where the intermediate scattered state is also a real electronic state, rather than a virtual state as in standard second-order Raman processes.[25] This provides a significant enhancement to scattering probabilities and is used extensively to account for the second-order resonant scattering processes in graphene and TMDs.[26–35] While momentum conservation ($\mathbf{q} \approx 0$ selection rule) limits first-order Raman-active phonons to those near the Brillouin zone (BZ) centre (Γ), higher-order scattering processes can involve phonons with larger wavevectors ($\mathbf{q}_i \neq 0$), provided the sum of those wavevectors throughout the scattering processes is zero.[36] In graphene, a defect-activated DRR feature known as the "D mode" allows sensitive defect detection and differentiation of armchair and zigzag edges due to real-space and reciprocal space backscattering conditions, making it a powerful tool for nanomaterials characterization.[25, 37] While DRR modes are prolific in

TMD materials, to the best of our knowledge no such *resonant defect mode* has yet been reported for MoS₂ or other TMDs.

In this work, we demonstrate for the first time a set of *resonant defect modes* in MoS₂ analogous to the D mode of graphene, which appear as a result of phonon coupling during indirect resonances in the presence of crystal edges and defects. We show that at 785 nm excitation (1.58 eV) an indirect resonance from Γ to K alongside an elastic scattering from an edge-defect results in intense features from single acoustic phonons in the Raman spectrum. In addition, we show that these modes exhibit an analogous incident polarization dependence to the D mode of graphene,[38] indicating the presence of an inhomogeneous optical absorption which selects for electron wavevectors perpendicular to the laser polarization direction.[39] Not only does indirect double resonance Raman provide a simple and effective probe of defect density and location, but the ability to identify MoS₂ edge structures, in particular, will have significant impact on the design and characterization of MoS₂ nanomaterials, where the distinction between zigzag and armchair edges defines the electronic, magnetic, and spin-valley polarization properties of the material.

2 Methods

MoS₂ samples were prepared from synthetic crystals (purchased from 2D Semiconductors) via the scotch tape method on polished sapphire substrates (purchased from SPI Supplies). Raman spectra were collected using a home-built low-frequency scanning Raman microscope. 532 nm, 633 nm and 785 nm excitation from solid-state diode laser sources was spectrally filtered using OptiGrate BragGrate bandpass filters, then focused onto the sample using a 100 \times oil immersion objective. Backscattered radiation was collected and passed through a set of OptiGrate BragGrate low-frequency notch filters to remove the elastically scattered laser light whilst preserving the Stokes and anti-Stokes scattering. The filtered light was then directed to a Princeton Instruments LS785 spectrograph (18 μ m slit width) and PIXIS 400BR eXcelon CCD camera for detection at 785 nm excitation, or a Princeton Instruments FERGIE (50 μ m slit width) for detection at 633 nm and 532 nm excitation. Incident laser power for crystals on sapphire was kept below 2 mW for 532 nm and 633 nm excitation, and 5 mW for 785 nm excitation to avoid sample damage. For powdered samples with poor thermal dissipation, this power was kept at sub-milliwatt levels. Simultaneous collection of Stokes and anti-Stokes scattering provided confirmation that laser-induced heating was not occurring in these spectra. Incident polarization was controlled via half-wave plates, and analysed polarization was controlled using a polarizing filter in the path of the collection optics.

Sonicated samples were prepared using common literature methods.[40] Briefly, commercially obtained powder (Sigma Aldrich, $\sim 1\mu$ m particle size) was dispersed in a 4:1 mix of dimethylformamide:deionised water, then sonicated using a 600 W 20 kHz horn sonicator in pulsed mode (10 seconds on, 5 seconds off) for 3 hours. The resulting dispersion was centrifuged several times at increasing speeds, recovering the pellet and re-centrifuging the supernatant.

Peak fitting was performed using Python and SciPy's least squares algorithm to optimize the fits of Lorentzian and pseudo-Voigt functions to the data.

Electronic band structure and phonon dispersions were calculated using density functional theory implemented by Quantum ESPRESSO[41–43] using the generalised gradient approximation and Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof functional (GGA-PBE).[44] Normconserving Vanderbilt (ONCV) pseudopotentials[45, 46] were used with a plane-wave cutoff of 120 Ry. The Brillouin zone was sampled with a $12 \times 12 \times 4$ Monkhorst-Pack grid. The phonon dispersion was obtained using Fourier interpolation of a grid of explicitly calculated frequencies on a $6 \times 6 \times 1$ grid of k points. Long-range non-covalent interactions were included using Grimme's semiempirical DFT-D2 correction.[47]

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Indirect Resonance Edge Modes

Figure 1 shows the Raman spectra of a flake of bulk mechanically exfoliated MoS₂ at three excitation energies: 532 nm (non-resonant), 633 nm (direct resonance), and 785 nm (indirect resonance). For each excitation wavelength, spectra were taken at edge and basal plane regions marked in the optical image in Figure 1c, which corresponds to the linescan data shown in Figure 1d and Figure S1.

Figure 1: Resonance Raman spectra of bulk MoS₂ flakes in basal plane and edge regions, indicated on the optical image in (c). AFM image and height data for this flake can be provided in Figure S2. (a) Spectra at 532 nm, 633 nm, and 785 nm excitation wavelengths represent off-resonance, direct-resonance at the K point of the BZ, and indirect resonance, respectively. (b) Zoom of the low-frequency region of the lower panel of (a) showing the defect modes at 785 nm excitation. Spectra are taken from the linescans in (c) (for 785 nm) and in Figure S1 (for 532 nm and 633 nm). The scale bar in (c) is 10 μm. (d) The linescan at 785 nm, zoomed in on the intensities of the edge modes for clarity. An alternative logarithmic scale representation for this scan is provided in Figure S3.

The spectra in Figure 1a are normalised to the most intense feature, with the edge spectrum offset above the basal plane spectrum for clarity. At each excitation wavelength, the fundamental first order E_{2g} and A_{1g} modes are visible near 383 cm⁻¹ and 408 cm⁻¹ respectively. It should be immediately clear that at 532 nm and 633 nm excitation there is no difference between the edge and basal plane spectra. However, for 785 nm excitation a set of features (shown clearly in Figure 1b) become prominent in the 100–250 cm⁻¹ region, with peaks near 238, 188, 177, and 150 cm⁻¹. The linescan in Figure 1c shows that these modes are localised at the edges, with little to no intensity in the basal plane region. Additionally, an order of magnitude enhancement in the E_{2g} intensity is observed at the edges, which is actually part of a general enhancement of the entire Raman spectrum (see Figure S4 and Figure S5), and appears to be the result of a pre-resonant excitation (discussed below). A pre-resonance occurs when all of the vibronic states near a particular resonance are close enough to start receiving some resonance enhancement, but none are necessarily close enough to have significantly larger enhancement than the next

closest state. As such, rather than observing one strongly enhanced mode, a set of weakly enhanced modes are observed. The frequencies of these features are too low to be first-order optical phonons (see Figure S6), and may instead originate from either defect-mediated acoustic phonons, or second-order difference bands.[48, 49]

Defect induced features for MoS₂ in the 100–250 cm⁻¹ region have been well reported in literature,[32, 50, 51] and it is generally accepted that they are the sum of interactions with many different normally Raman-inactive acoustic phonons from across the BZ. These modes appear as a consequence of elastic scattering by defects and a breakdown of the wave vector $\mathbf{q} \approx 0$ selection rule in crystalline materials, imprinting the spectrum with phonon density of states (pDOS) like features. A saddle point in the LA branches of the phonon dispersion between M and K results in a high pDOS near 220 cm⁻¹. [48, 52] As such, broad features in this region are usually the first identifiable "defect modes", and are generally regarded as an indication of poor crystallinity[50] or small particle size.[51](see Figure S7)

However, the features in Figure 1b are sharp and intense, and the 238 cm⁻¹ feature does not align with the pDOS maxima near 220 cm⁻¹, suggesting it has a specific resonant origin. Similar features have been briefly reported by Placidi et al., but only in the basal plane of MoS₂. [53] They attribute their origin to a defect mediated indirect resonance, assuming planar stacking faults as the defects.

Two-phonon resonant Raman scattering occurs through an indirect band gap by absorbing (or emitting) a phonon (\mathbf{q}_1) with the matching symmetry and wavevector of the band gap, followed by emission (or absorption) of a second phonon, \mathbf{q}_2 , that satisfies $\mathbf{q}_2 = -\mathbf{q}_1$. [54] Consequently, indirect resonance Raman scattering enhances second order features which satisfy momentum and energy conservation, and possess the appropriate symmetry to cross the BZ. By contrast, elastic scattering by defects can also satisfy momentum conservation, resulting in enhancement of single phonon features. For instance, the band near 238 cm⁻¹ has a frequency matching a single LA phonon from either the M or K points,[48] suggesting this band results from a phonon-defect-mediated indirect transition from Γ_v to M_c ($\overline{\Gamma M}$) or Γ_v to K_c ($\overline{\Gamma K}$) (subscripts v and c denote valence and conduction bands respectively). A (\overline{KQ}) transition mediated by M phonons is very close in frequency to the $\overline{\Gamma M}$ transition (see Figure S6)[55, 56] which makes assignments based on frequency alone difficult in this case.[30]

Analysis of the allowed combinations of phonon and state symmetries is complicated by the fact that the indirect transitions at 1.58 eV excitation allows nesting of the band structures, since they can join a range of initial states near Γ_v and final states surrounding the local conduction band minima, provided a phonon can mediate the transition (see Figure S8). Thus any number of initial and final states near the high symmetry points may be involved with various symmetry combinations, and neither K nor M phonons can be necessarily excluded.

Such phonon-defect interactions are characteristic of the D mode in graphene, and a similar DRR model can be used to describe the processes in MoS₂. While specific resonance conditions can arise as a consequence of symmetry and quantum mechanical interference,[57] it is convenient to consider the scattering process using a real space model.[37, 58] During the indirect transition, the excited electron is imparted with a significant quanta of crystal momentum by the scattered phonon. In MoS₂, tightly bound excitons correlate electron and hole motion, and propagate through the lattice with a non-zero centre of mass momentum in a direction predominantly defined by the phonon wavevector. Upon reaching an edge of the crystal, diffraction of the charge carrier wavefunctions at the boundary results in a reflection-like behaviour of the exciton (see Figure 2). As such a straight edge can only impart momentum perpendicular to the edge direction,[38] and a reciprocal space backscatter condition can only be satisfied when charge carriers impact at an angle perpendicular to the edge direction. Delocalisation of the edge defect in reciprocal space allows it assume any scattering wavevectors along this perpendicular direction.[59]

This incident angular dependence constitutes an additional real space backscatter condition,

Figure 2: (a) Representation of the armchair and zigzag edge structures, and the direction of the scattering wavevectors by each edge. Armchair edges provide wavevectors (\mathbf{k}_{ac}) in the $\overline{\Gamma K}$ direction, while zigzag edges scatter in the $\overline{\Gamma M}$ direction (\mathbf{k}_{zz}). (b) Representation of reflection at an edge, indicating that in order for all of the phonon momentum to be cancelled (backscatter), the charge carriers must impact perpendicular to the edge direction.

and results in a selection rule for different edge structures. Since armchair and zigzag edges are rotated 30° from each other, we expect armchair edges to only satisfy the backscatter constraints for phonons whose wavevectors lie along the $\overline{\Gamma K}$ direction, and zigzag edges to only backscatter phonons along the $\overline{\Gamma M}$ direction (see Figure 2). This selection rule applies only to straight edges, as irregular edges may allow backscattering for oblique incidences if the local edge geometry is sufficiently disordered.[38]

In order to help distinguish between K and M phonons in our edge spectra, we can compare two edges oriented either 30° , 90° or 150° from each other. The hexagonal symmetry of the crystal means that we can expect one of these edges to have predominantly armchair structure and the other to have predominantly zigzag structure. The top-right corner of the flake in Figure 1c appears to be a 90° corner, and Figure 3 shows spectra taken from each edge, indicated by the arrows labelled "X" and "Y". These spectra were taken at both room temperature and low temperature (~ 70 K) to identify contributions from second-order difference bands in the acoustic region, as such features involve absorption of a thermally excited phonon and become considerably less probable at low temperatures. From this point on we collectively refer to the features in the $100\text{-}250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ spectral region as "defect modes".

At room temperature the spectra of the X-edge, Y-edge and basal plane share many similarities in the defect modes (Figure 3a-c). However, at low temperature the defect modes from the Y-edge in (b) and basal plane in (c) completely disappear, indicating these are indeed second-order difference bands. In the X-edge spectra in (a) we see a similar loss of difference band features, but with three distinct peaks remaining near 238 cm^{-1} , 188 cm^{-1} , and 150 cm^{-1} , which we temporarily assign the labels $p1$, $p2$, and $p3$, respectively. These appear to be signatures from first-order acoustic phonons resulting from a one-phonon one-defect mediated indirect transition. The fourth peak in Figure 1b near 177 cm^{-1} disappears at low temperature, indicating a difference band, likely the $A_{1g}(M)\text{-}LA'(M)$ mode observed under resonant conditions,[49] and its enhancement at the edges is discussed below. While temperature changes can shift the electronic band energies and alter the resonance condition, it should be noted that the appearance of the broad resonant feature near 450 cm^{-1} (commonly referred to as the 2LA band), and additional combination bands above 500 cm^{-1} indicate a resonant transition is still being achieved at low temperature (see Figure S10). The diminished intensity of these second-order features at low temperature is likely a consequence of such shifts, where an increasing band gap

Figure 3: Spectra taken from each of the positions indicated in Figure 1c, taken at both room-temperature (RT) and $\sim 70\text{K}$ (LT). The X-edge (a) shows three key defect modes remain at LT, while the Y-edge (b) loses all signals in this region, suggesting that these modes are in fact difference bands. The modes at RT on the Y-edge show remarkable similarity to the difference bands in the basal plane (c), suggesting they share the same resonant origin (see Figure S9 for overlain spectra).

moves these features away from resonance. Conversely, the intensity of $p1$ in Figure 3a actually increases with respect to the E_{2g} mode, suggesting that low temperature shifts the band structure towards resonance with this mode.

3.2 Mode Assignments

The use of tunable lasers to fine-tune the resonance condition is a common method for following the dispersion of DRR modes, which can help identify the origin of the resonant pathways through reference to the phonon dispersion and observing their resonance onset. Our Raman configuration lacks tunable excitation capability, but since TMDs display layer dependent electronic structures,[60–62] we can instead use layer number to shift the band gap relative to a fixed excitation energy. As layer number decreases and the band gap increases, we would expect a \overline{KQ} or $\overline{\Gamma M}$ (M phonon) resonance to be lost before a $\overline{\Gamma K}$ or $\overline{\Gamma Q}$ resonance, with the remaining modes being K and Q phonons at armchair edges (see Figures S8 and S6).

Figure 4a shows a linescan across a flake with both thick and thin sections, as indicated by the optical contrast and quantified by atomic force microscopy (see Figure S11 and Table S1). The linescan follows the direction of the vertical arrow "V" in Figure 4b, moving first across the thickest section (> 60 layers) which assumes bulk properties, before crossing the thinnest section in the middle (5 layers). The bottom section is one layer thicker than the middle section (6 layers). When crossing the thick section in the first $8 \mu\text{m}$, clear peaks in the linescan are observed at both the outer and inner edges for all modes, which drop down to a baseline in the centre of the thick triangular section around $4.5 \mu\text{m}$. Notably, all the Raman bands reach a maximum intensity at the same scan position, as indicated by the dotted lines. Moving across the thin basal plane ($8\text{--}17 \mu\text{m}$) shows no significant spectral changes, until the edge of the bottom section is encountered around $18.5 \mu\text{m}$. At this point $p1$ peaks again, and the E_{2g} mode begins to climb. However, for this thin edge, $p1$ reaches its maxima when the E_{2g} signal is approximately half way towards its maximum intensity for this section. This is also observed at the bottom

edge of the flake around $25 \mu\text{m}$. Logically, this is the expected behaviour for individual edge and basal plane signals when a circular laser spot is scanned over the edge towards the basal plane (see Figure 4d). This is easier to see in the horizontal linescan shown in Figure 4c, which runs through the thin middle section only.

Figure 4: (a) Linescan plot of the key Raman band intensities while scanning across the flake in (b), in the direction of the vertical arrow "V". (b) Optical image of a flake with thick (purple triangle at top) and thin (blue sections middle and bottom) flake sections. The scale bar in (b) is $10 \mu\text{m}$. (c) Linescan of the horizontal arrow labelled "H". (d) Schematic of the expected trend in intensities for edge and basal plane modes while scanning across the edge of a flake into the basal plane. Note the "*" in the legend next to $p1$ indicates its intensity has been multiplied by a factor of 3 for clarity.

Figure 5 shows as layer number decreases further, $p1$, $p2$, and $p3$ all remain in the spectrum down to few-layer thickness (see Figure S12 and Table S2 for AFM data). These modes are still present at bilayer thickness (see Figure S13) which has the largest indirect band gap before becoming direct in single layer. In the bilayer spectrum, the defect modes at an edge are more intense than the fundamental modes, which suggests an improving resonance condition as the band gap approaches the excitation energy. A dispersion of $p1$ to higher frequency is also observed as layer number decreases (Figure 5b), which is a consequence of the real states accessed by the phonon scatterings, and a behaviour which distinguishes DRR modes from standard second-order processes. It should be noted that the AFM data in Figure S12 is not intended to quantify the dispersion of peak frequency with layer number, but simply show that the trend can be observed.

Figures 4 and 5 show that as layer number decreases, the defect-mediated resonant features of the Y-edge are lost, while the X-edge defect modes remain and become enhanced. Consequently, we conclude that the Y-edge difference band features shown in Figure 3 arise from the higher energy \overline{KQ} or $\overline{\Gamma M}$ pre-resonant transitions via M phonons, and the X-edge features $p1$, $p2$, and

Figure 5: (a) Linescan of flake in (c) in the direction of the arrow, with intensities extracted via peak fitting. The dotted lines for 460 cm⁻¹ (2LA) and 383 cm⁻¹ (E_{2g}) indicate that the intensities of these lines have been normalised (reduced) to match the defect modes for clarity. The vertical lines correlate the scan position to the dots in (b). (b) A plot of the peak fitted frequency of *p1* against scan position, showing an increase in frequency as the flake becomes thinner, indicating the mode is dispersing due to the increasing band gap (AFM data in Figure S12). Scale bar in (c) is 10 μm.

p3 shown in Figure 3a arise from the lower energy $\overline{\Gamma\text{K}}$ and $\overline{\Gamma\text{Q}}$ transitions via K and Q phonons respectively. The backscatter constraint then identifies the Y-edge as the armchair edge, and the X-edge as the zigzag edge. We can then assign *p1* to an LA(K) phonon, and tentatively assign the main mode of *p2* to a TA(K) phonon. *p2* may also contain contributions from LA(Q) phonons mediating a $\overline{\Gamma\text{Q}}$ transition, but the pDOS at LA(Q) is significantly smaller than at TA(K), suggesting a lower probability of transition (see Figure S6.[48]) In addition, the relatively small frequency difference between the TA(K) and ZA(K) phonons and asymmetric *p2* peak shape, even at low temperature, implies that unresolved contributions from the ZA(K) phonons may also be present on the low-frequency side of the *p2* peak (see Figure S14). However, the asymmetry could also contain an imprint of the relatively large pDOS near this frequency as a result of non-resonant defect scatterings. The frequency of *p3* is too low to be a K phonon, and is therefore likely a TA(Q) phonon mediating the $\overline{\Gamma\text{Q}}$ transition.

In thin samples, the 177 cm⁻¹ mode intensity is localised in the basal plane (see Figure S15), indicating its enhancement in Figure 1 is due to excitation via the higher energy pre-resonances, and supports its assignment as the M point difference band A_{1g}(M)-LA'(M) observed in literature.[49] Since the states at Γ_v and Q_c have strong contributions from the sulfur p_z orbitals,[63] the $\overline{\Gamma\text{Q}}$ and $\overline{\Gamma\text{K}}$ gap energies follow the same trends with temperature and layer number, making identification of one particular pathway using these methods challenging. Further studies using band gap engineering techniques and tunable excitation lasers may help isolate a particular resonant pathway.[32, 64] Nevertheless, since these transitions both require M phonons, we will refer to them collectively for now as the "M-resonance".

It should be noted that following the dispersion of features in *p2* to identify their assignments is significantly more challenging due to the presence of underlying difference bands (see Figure 7c below), and the inherently lower absorption probabilities for indirect resonances (compared to direct resonances). Consequently, the acquisition times for these spectra are an order of magnitude longer than typical (direct) double resonance Raman studies. A variable excitation study would allow one to measure the $\overline{\Gamma\text{K}}$ and $\overline{\Gamma\text{Q}}$ indirect resonances at thicker edges, which would reduce acquisition times by providing a larger amount of edges (layers) in the scattering volume at the ideal resonance energies. In addition, the sequential onset of resonances to the Q

and K points as excitation energy is swept across the conduction band minimum should facilitate differentiation the Q and K components of $p2$.

3.3 Defect Quantification

The appearance of specific defect modes in MoS₂ provides a convenient means of identifying and quantifying defects in MoS₂ materials. For powders and rotationally-averaged materials, the LA(K) mode provides a sensitive reporter for defects, which should find particular use in the characterization of catalytic MoS₂ material. Figure 6 shows the Raman spectra of a series of sonicated MoS₂ nanoparticles, which are purified into fractions of decreasing average size (increasing number of edges) using differential centrifugation. In these samples the defect modes dominate the spectrum and can be used as a measure of defect density, reported as a ratio of LA(K) to the fundamental A_{1g} or E_{2g} modes, similar to current literature methods.[32, 50] In addition, second-order modes appear near 425 cm⁻¹ and 480 cm⁻¹, which correspond to the LA(K)+TA(K) DRR mode reported by Carvalho et al.[30] and 2LA(K) mode respectively.

However, this method comes with some caveats and care must be taken to ensure an accurate result is reported. For instance, it appears in these samples that the bulk M-resonance is absent, likely due to the exfoliation of MoS₂ into thin layers via the sonication method. Should the sample exhibit such a resonance, or a laser be used which can access it, the fundamental modes will be enhanced by the pre-resonance and such a ratio of modes will not give an accurate result. When examining discrete crystal systems, the structure of the edge (armchair and zigzag) will affect the intensity of the defect modes. Nevertheless, these constraints should in fact be beneficial to the study of nanomaterials, since the two edge structures are known to manifest different physical properties. This also applies to other defects such as grain boundaries, which can be observed in CVD-grown MoS₂ as a spike in the LA(K) mode (see Figure S16). Indirect double resonance Raman spectroscopy therefore provides a powerful tool for the characterization and optimization of MoS₂ nanomaterials.

Figure 6: Spectra of a series of MoS₂ nanoparticles of decreasing particle size. The spectra labels indicate increasing centrifugation speed, and therefore "1" indicates the largest particle sizes while "6" indicates the smallest. The defect modes dominate the spectrum in these samples (left panel), and new second-order features between 410 cm⁻¹ and 500 cm⁻¹ become prominent in the panel on the right. The peak near 480 cm⁻¹ matches the frequency of the 2LA(K) mode.

3.4 Polarization Dependence

We also note that the defect modes display an incident polarization dependence fully analogous to the polarization dependence of the D mode of graphene. Figure 7(b) shows the peak fitted intensities for the LA(K) and TA(K) peaks as a function θ_{in} , which is the angular difference between the edge direction and incident polarization vector. The solid and dashed traces are optimized fits of

$$I = I_{max} - I_{min} \cos^2 \theta_{in} \quad (1)$$

where I_{max} and I_{min} are the maximum and minimum intensities for each frequency across all polarization angles.[38] For mostly armchair edge structures, I_{min}/I_{max} approaches zero, while for mostly zigzag edge structures I_{min}/I_{max} approaches one. The LA(K) mode shows a strong polarization dependence, with an I_{min}/I_{max} of 0.094, which indicates well ordered but not perfect edges, as the mode does not drop to zero at perpendicular angles. This matches expectations, since although an edge may appear straight in optical images, it is often disordered at micro and nanoscales.[38, 65] In addition, it is likely that for multi-layered flakes such as this, not all of the layers under the laser spot have the same edge structure. In general, armchair edges give polarization dependent defect mode intensities, while zigzag edges give no defect mode intensity, and for disordered edges the ratio of armchair and zigzag segments is proportional to I_{min}/I_{max} .

Figure 7: (a) Optical image of thin flakes. Scale bar is 10 μm . The green circle indicates the point at which the polarization data in (b) was taken. (b) A polar plot of the peak fitted intensities of the LA(K) (blue) and TA(K) (orange) modes, normalised to I_{max} for clarity. The dots indicate data points while the solid trace is the optimized fit of equation 1. (c) Raman maps of the flake in (a) at the indicated frequencies, with the orientation of the incident polarization vector indicated by the arrow labelled "P".

In graphene, the polarization dependence is a consequence of a unique inhomogeneous optical absorption coefficient around the K point, which results in a $|\mathbf{P} \times \mathbf{k}_e|^2$ dependence on the probability of absorption, where \mathbf{k}_e is the electron wavevector and \mathbf{P} is the linear polarization

vector of incident radiation.[39] The effect is not observed in the basal plane due to the hexagonal symmetry of the BZ, but at an edge where symmetry is broken and wavevector dependencies arise, a clear $\cos^2\theta_{in}$ dependence on the D mode intensity is observed which can reveal additional insights such as the ratio of armchair and zigzag edges at a particular point.[38] The inhomogeneous absorption was predicted to be unique to graphene due to the linear dispersion of the electronic band structure near K, and absent in other materials with quadratic dispersions.[39] Nevertheless, we observe an identical polarization dependence for the K point defect modes in MoS₂, suggesting a similar inhomogeneous absorption may exist in MoS₂.

The TA(K)/*p*2 mode has a higher I_{min}/I_{max} value of 0.233, which is a consequence of a larger I_{min} due to underlying second-order difference bands from the basal plane, as well as possible contributions from non-resonant defect scattering (i.e. the pDOS signature). These effects can be seen in the maps of 188 cm⁻¹ in Figure 7c as intensity in the interior of the flake. The same limitations apply to *p*3 (see Figure S17 for plots). However, because LA(K) sits on the upper frequency limit of the pDOS for acoustic phonons and is the most intense of the three modes, there is very little background and it provides an excellent unambiguous reporter for edge defects.

Assuming MoS₂ exhibits an inhomogeneous optical absorption, we can describe the origin of the polarization dependence using a similar mechanism to that of the D mode in graphene. The electron-phonon scattering matrix elements of the indirect transition impart a $\mathbf{k}_e \cdot \mathbf{q}$ dependence on the scattering probability,[36] while an inhomogeneous optical absorption provides a $\mathbf{P} \times \mathbf{k}_e$ dependence on the absorption coefficient, such that electron wavevectors perpendicular to the incident polarization direction are favoured. Thus an incident polarization vector parallel to the edge direction maximises the probability of exciting an electron with wavevector perpendicular to the edge, which in turn maximises the probability of scattering via a phonon that satisfies the backscatter condition.

Interestingly, we also observe a polarization dependence on the intensity of features enhanced by the M-resonance, which is not necessarily expected since these transitions are mediated entirely via second-order phonon modes and can conserve momentum without the need for an edge defect backscatter. Unlike the $\overline{\Gamma K}$ resonance, this dependence is present at both zigzag and armchair edges, with maximum intensities at parallel polarization to the edge direction, regardless of edge structure (Figure 8). Normalising features to the E_{2g} mode (lower row of Figure 8a/b) shows that all the M-resonant features are affected proportionally. This, in combination with the fact that the enhancement is present on both edges, suggests the dependence is a consequence of wavevector conservation rather than crystallographic orientation, or the polarization dependence of any specific mode or modes.

We suggest that although not required for observation of Raman modes, the backscatter at an edge may enable additional phonon wavevector combinations to satisfy momentum conservation (see Figure SII.1). Figure 9 shows a schematic of some two-phonon interactions that become allowed in combination with an edge scattering event. Since an edge backscatter results in momentum conservation for phonon wavevectors perpendicular to the edge, then any phonon wavevectors (yellow arrows) whose sum is a new wavevector perpendicular to the edge (blue arrows) will become allowed. Without the edge, only the \mathbf{q} , $-\mathbf{q}$ combinations are active. The increased number of allowed combinations at an edge leads to an increased probability that a scattering process can occur via this pathway, resulting in higher intensities at the edges. The angular dependence of electron-phonon scattering matrix elements enhances combinations of electron and phonon wavevectors for angles which are closer to parallel rather than perpendicular, leading to a similar $\cos^2\theta_{in}$ dependence as the $\overline{\Gamma K}$ resonance. This explanation implies that the enhancement effects should not disappear at polarizations perpendicular to the edges, since in such a case there are still non-zero probabilities that phonons with wavevectors at 30° and 60° to the edges can interact with another phonon to give a wavevector sum perpendicular to the edge and satisfy the backscatter constraints. Indeed we observe resonance enhancement

Figure 8: Polar plots of the polarization dependence of the M-resonance, at both X and Y-edges ((a/b) respectively). The top row shows raw peak fitted intensities, while the bottom row shows those intensities normalised to the E_{2g} mode. I_{min}/I_{max} values are listed in Table S3.

even at perpendicular polarizations at both edges (Figure S18). The appearance of the polarization dependence may also be compounded by effects of the finite lifetimes of the excited state charge carriers travelling at different angles towards the edges, as described by Casiraghi et al. for graphene modes.[38] This model also explains the enhancement of the 2LA(K) feature in the powder samples of Figure 6, and its polarization dependence in thin flakes without any contribution from the M-resonance (see Figure S19).

Figure 9: Schematic representation of wavevector combinations that become allowed via momentum conservation upon edge scattering. The yellow arrows indicate the individual phonon wavevectors, while the blue arrows indicate their sum. Any two phonons whose wavevectors sum to be perpendicular to an edge become allowed following an edge backscatter.

We note, however, that the A_{1g} exhibits an anomalous polarization dependence, with a maximum intensity when the incident polarization is perpendicular (rather than parallel) to the edge. One possible explanation is that in-plane anisotropy is induced by the broken symmetry of the edge, which is known to result in a polarization dependence for the A_{1g} mode of 2D materials.[66] However, no such dependence is observed in thin samples, indicating that the effect is specifically related to the M-resonance and may be a consequence of electron-phonon

coupling between the states. We do not yet have a detailed explanation for this behaviour, and leave its analysis to future work.

4 Conclusion

We have demonstrated a defect-mediated indirect DRR mechanism in MoS₂ which results in the observation of normally forbidden acoustic phonons and second-order DRR modes. The defect-mediated single phonon modes are analogous to the D mode in graphene, and phonon selection from high symmetry points is limited by strict backscatter constraints in real and reciprocal space, enabling the differentiation between armchair and zigzag edge structures. This is, to the best of our knowledge, the first report of such resonant defect modes in MoS₂. Unlike graphene where the photon absorption processes are considered as direct transitions, the MoS₂ defect modes arise as a consequence of the coupling to $\mathbf{q} \neq 0$ phonons required to mediate indirect transitions throughout the BZ.

By utilising the shifting band gap of MoS₂ with layer number, we have identified two resonant pathways: Γ_v to K_c , and Γ_v to Q_c . We have shown that the feature near 238 cm⁻¹ (*p1*) can be assigned to the LA(K) phonon, and the feature near 150 cm⁻¹ (*p3*) can be assigned to a TA(Q) phonon. The feature near 188 cm⁻¹ (*p2*) is likely due to a convolution of TA(K), ZA(K), and LA(Q) phonons from their respective resonant pathways. Due to the real-space backscatter condition, these features are only observed at armchair edges, thereby enabling the differentiation of edge structure and crystallographic orientation. A general enhancement of the entire spectrum irrespective of edge orientation is attributed to a pre-resonance from Γ_v to M_c or K_v to M_c , which is lost as layer number decreases and the band gap increases away from resonance.

Since the edges and defects of MoS₂ are known to be the active catalytic sites for the hydrogen evolution reaction, this technique provides a means of screening the catalytic potential of synthesised MoS₂ materials, and also may provide insights into the mechanisms which cause active site passivation and catalyst performance degradation. While non-resonant pDOS features have been used for defect quantification in the past, this method offers much greater sensitivity, and provides a means of characterizing defects and grain boundaries in otherwise pristine crystals.

Lastly, since these defect modes are sensitive to electronic structure, applications of indirect DRR at this and other excitation energies may extend to characterization of a vast family of van der Waals heterostructures, TMD nanomaterials, and other semiconductor systems. Given an appropriate excitation energy, we anticipate the ability to identify analogous defect modes in similar TMDs such as MoSe₂, WS₂, and WSe₂.

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5.1 Edge modes of MoS₂ via Indirect Double Resonant Raman Spectroscopy

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5.3 Supplementary I: Additional Figures

Figure S1: Linescans along the arrow indicated in Figure 1d at 785 nm, 633 nm, and 532 nm excitations. The edge and basal plane region spectra in 1a are extracted from these linescans, indicated by the circle and star for edge and basal plane regions respectively.

Figure S2: (a) AFM image and (b) height profile of the flake shown in Figure 1c indicating hundreds of layers and therefore bulk electronic properties.

Figure S3: The same 785 nm excitation linescan as in Figure 1d and Figure S1, but on a logarithmic scale to show the relative enhancement of spectral features at the edges.

Linescan of Y-edge

Figure S4: Linescan over the Y-edge, showing that M-resonance enhancement affects the whole spectrum on thick edges, not just the defect modes.

Linescan of X-edge

Figure S5: Linescan over the X-edge, showing that M-resonance enhancement affects the whole spectrum on the armchair edge of thick samples as well as the zigzag edge.

Figure S6: (a) Bulk 2H-MoS₂ band structure with arrows indicating the possible indirect transitions. The colour of the arrow matches the colours in (b), where the arrows indicate the 2D Brillouin zone wavevectors mediating those transitions. Note that in (b) the dotted line indicates a translation of the "M" wavevector to K, showing that M phonons can mediate a $\bar{K}\bar{Q}$ transition. (c) The calculated phonon dispersion and density of states for bulk MoS₂. (d) A zoom of the phonon dispersion near M and K.

Figure S7: The same sonicated samples in Figure 6 recorded under 633 nm excitation, normalised to the E_{2g} (left) and A_{1g} (right) fundamental modes. The inset shows the defect mode region, and a broad feature near 230 cm^{-1} can be seen emerging in the most sonicated samples.

Figure S8: Indirect transitions can be made to/from states across the Brillouin zone, provided a phonon with the appropriate wavevector and symmetry is available. States in the valence and conduction bands sharing the same colour of horizontal stripe are approximately 1.58 eV apart (785 nm excitation), and allowed by energy conservation. This allows a type of limited band nesting, where a range of initial and final states may be involved in indirect transitions - defined by the state and phonon symmetries, and the density of phonon states of a given wavevector. Arrows indicate some possible resonant transitions, and dashed arrows indicate possible pathways for observed pre-resonant transitions.

Figure S9: An overlay of the defect mode region of the X edge, Y edge and basal plane spectra in Figure 3 and Figure S10, showing the similarities in their features.

Figure S10: The same X edge, Y edge and basal plane spectra from Figure 3 showing a larger spectral region with the fundamental modes, 2LA feature, and other second-order DRR modes. The low temperature spectra show a decrease in the relative intensity of the second-order modes, indicating the resonance condition is weaker but is not lost under these conditions.

Figure S11: (a) AFM image of the flake in 4, showing the lines used for extracting profiles and layer number quantification. (b-d) Samples of the line profiles. Additional values for the line profiles can be found in Table S1.

Table S1: Table of step heights for the AFM line profiles indicated in Figure S11

Line	Step height (nm)	Average	Est. layers
1	3.955	3.907	5
2	3.904		
3	3.863		
4	5.029	4.803	6
5	4.351		
6	5.030		
7	48.116	48.116	60

Figure S12: AFM image of the flake in 5. (b) Height profile of the line in (a), with the step height values listed in table S2.

Steps	Step height (nm)
1-2	2.472
2-3	0.446
3-4	0.889
4-5	0.536
5-6	0.793

Table S2: Layer heights calculated from each of the fitted lines in S12b.

Figure S13: (a) Raman spectra of a bilayer flake of MoS₂ at 785 nm excitation, taken in the basal plane (left) and at an edge (right) near the line indicated in (b). Note the LA(K) is significantly more intense than the E_{2g} in bilayer systems due to the favourable resonance with the band gap in thin MoS₂. (b) AFM image of the flake used for the spectra in (a). (c) Height profile of the MoS₂ flake, indicating bilayer thickness.

5.4 Edge modes of MoS₂ via Indirect Double Resonant Raman Spectroscopy

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Y-edge			
Frequency (cm ⁻¹)	I_{\min}	I_{\max}	I_{\min}/I_{\max}
238	189.5809	553.1953	0.3427
188	644.8647	2383.8295	0.2705
149	512.3803	2386.399	0.2147
X-edge			
Frequency (cm ⁻¹)	I_{\min}	I_{\max}	I_{\min}/I_{\max}
238	866.7753	10019.4305	0.0865
188	538.6813	4043.4702	0.1332
149	389.5278	2909.6225	0.1339
Y-edge normalised to E _{2g}			
Frequency (cm ⁻¹)	I_{\min}	I_{\max}	I_{\min}/I_{\max}
238	0.0093	0.0073	1.2744
188	0.0327	0.0327	1.0002
149	0.0273	0.0335	0.8162
X-edge normalised to E _{2g}			
Frequency (cm ⁻¹)	I_{\min}	I_{\max}	I_{\min}/I_{\max}
238	0.0917	0.2446	0.375
188	0.0494	0.0968	0.5106
149	0.0359	0.0695	0.5169

Table S3: I_{\min} and I_{\max} values for the polarization plots for in Figure 8

Figure S14: The p_2 peak at low temperature shows asymmetry with a tail on the low frequency side, indicating the presence of additional underlying features or pDOS signatures. These may be ZA(K) phonons, LA(Q) phonons, or general pDOS features.

Figure S15: Additional Raman maps of the flake in Figure 7, and again in (a) for convenience. The left and right maps in (b) show that the E_{2g} (383 cm^{-1}) and $A_{1g}(M)$ -LA(M) (177 cm^{-1}) modes are localised in the basal plane of thin flakes, and not at the edges. These modes only receive resonant enhancement in bulk samples via the M pre-resonance.

Figure S16: (a) A linescan across the grain boundary formed between two inter-grown crystals shown in (b), synthesised by chemical vapour deposition (CVD). A clear peak in the LA(K) intensity is observed in the middle of the linescan where the boundary is expected to be located, indicating that the LA(K) can also be used to identify other defects such as grain boundaries. Incident polarization was perpendicular to the direction of travel. Scale bar in (b) is 10 μm

Figure S17: The polar plots of the three defect modes, taken from the thin edge in 7. Each peak is shown individually and with their I_{min}/I_{max} values listed in the legends. The larger I_{min}/I_{max} values in $p2$ and $p3$ are a consequence of their lower overall intensities and underlying difference bands and pDOS features.

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5.6 Supplementary II: Bulk Polarization Dependence - Wavevector Sums

If we assume the probability of an electron with wavevector \mathbf{e}_k being scattered by a phonon of wavevector \mathbf{q}_1 follows a $|\mathbf{e}_k \cdot \mathbf{q}_1|^2$ relationship, and that subsequent phonon scatterings also

Figure S18: Linescans of the X and Y-edges at perpendicular incident polarization, showing that the resonance enhancement persists at the edge, despite being in the opposite polarization to satisfy the edge backscatter constraint. As such, the M resonance must be mediated by second order phonons and a defect scattering.

follow a $|\mathbf{q}_1 \cdot \mathbf{q}_2|^2$ relationship, then we can sum the probabilities of each step towards the defect-activated wavevectors at each edge type (armchair and zigzag) to define the bulk two-phonon polarization dependence.

At the armchair edge, the M points in the Brillouin zone are located at 30° from the edge normal, meaning that excitation via two M phonons can take one of two paths at $\pm 30^\circ$ (a or b). The subsequent phonon required to sum to a perpendicular wavevector has its wavevector at 60° to the first phonon. Thus the two scattering pathways give a probability of $(a) + (b)$, where

$$(a) = \cos(\theta_{in} + 30) \cdot \cos(60)$$

$$(b) = \cos(\theta_{in} - 30) \cdot \cos(60)$$

At the zigzag edge, the M points are located at $\pm 60^\circ$ to the edge normal (c/e), with an additional M point running parallel to the edge normal (d). The subsequent phonon wavevectors are also at 60° from the initial phonon wavevector - except for the parallel wavevector, for which the subsequent interaction is at 0° . Including only the $\pm 60^\circ$ scattering pathways gives a polarization dependence where the intensity maxima is at perpendicular polarization, not parallel (Figure SII.2). As such, inclusion of the parallel pathway is required to match the experimental values for the polarization dependence, which indicates that the forward scattered two-phonon edge reflection is occurring in this model. Thus the scattering pathways $(c) + (d) + (e)$ gives a polarization profile which is a close match to the experimental data (Figure SII.2):

$$(c) = \cos(\theta_{in} + 60) \cdot \cos(60)$$

Figure S19: Peak fitted spectra of the thin flake polarization series in 7, showing the fundamental and 2LA region. A weak feature emerges at 480 cm^{-1} for parallel incident polarization with the edge, which we assign to a 2LA(K) combination which is activated by the defect backscatter.

$$(d) = \cos(0) \cdot \cos(0)$$

$$(e) = \cos(\theta_{in} - 60) \cdot \cos(60)$$

Figure SII.1: Schematic representation of the phonon wavevectors (yellow) and their sums (blue) for the zigzag and armchair edges. Phonon scattering combinations which sum to give a backscatter condition at an edge reflection are labelled (a) – (e). These correspond to the trigonometric equations discussed in the text.

Figure SII.2: Polar plots of the experimental E_{2g} intensities and fit of $\cos^2\theta_{in}$ at the X and Y-edges as a function of polarization angle from Figure 8. The red trace is the two-phonon wavevector sums of (a) – (e) at the corresponding edge, which shows a close match to the experimentally observed polarization dependence.